

The role of integrative projects in the human resources course at Fatec Zona Leste

*O papel dos projetos integradores no curso de recursos humanos
da Fatec Zona Leste*
*El papel de los proyectos integradores en el curso de recursos
humanos de Fatec Zona Leste*

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1 – FATEC Zona Leste

Abstract:

This paper discusses the importance of human capital in economic and social development, highlighting the evolution of professional skills from an emphasis on formal education to the development of soft skills. These skills are increasingly present in the job market and are valued by companies alongside technical skills. The study also explores the need for recent graduates to keep their skills up to date, as careers have become more fluid and diverse. Educational institutions play a crucial role in this scenario, and integrative projects are presented as effective tools for bringing students closer to the real demands of the job market. The aim of this article is to understand the role of integrative projects in the human resources management course at Fatec Zona Leste, with a focus on 5th and 6th semester students, and to investigate their contribution to training and preparing students for the job market.

Keywords: *Human Resources; Integrative Project; Job Market; Transversal Competencies.*

Resumo:

Este trabalho aborda a importância do capital humano no desenvolvimento econômico e social, destacando a evolução das competências profissionais, que passou da ênfase na educação formal para incluir o desenvolvimento de competências transversais, ou soft skills. Essas habilidades estão cada vez mais presentes no mercado de trabalho, sendo valorizadas pelas empresas junto com as competências técnicas. O estudo também explora a necessidade de profissionais recém-formados manterem suas habilidades atualizadas, já que as carreiras se tornaram mais fluidas e diversificadas. As instituições de ensino têm um papel crucial nesse cenário, e os projetos integradores são apresentados como ferramentas eficazes para aproximar os estudantes das demandas reais do mercado de trabalho. O objetivo deste artigo é compreender o papel dos projetos integradores no curso de gestão de recursos humanos da Fatec Zona Leste, com foco nos alunos do 5º e 6º semestre, e investigar sua contribuição para a formação e preparação dos estudantes para o mercado de trabalho.

Palavras-chave: Recursos Humanos; Projeto Integrador; Mercado de Trabalho;
Competências Transversais.

Resumen:

Este documento aborda la importancia del capital humano en el desarrollo económico y social, destacando la evolución de las competencias profesionales, que ha pasado de hacer hincapié en la educación formal a incluir el desarrollo de habilidades blandas. Estas competencias están cada vez más presentes en el mercado laboral y son valoradas por las empresas junto con las competencias técnicas. El estudio también explora la necesidad de que los recién licenciados mantengan actualizadas sus competencias, ya que las carreras profesionales se han vuelto más fluidas y diversas. Las instituciones educativas desempeñan un papel crucial en este escenario, y los proyectos integradores se presentan como herramientas eficaces para acercar a los estudiantes a las demandas reales del mercado laboral. El objetivo de este artículo es comprender el papel de los proyectos integradores en el curso de gestión de recursos humanos de Fatec Zona Leste, con especial atención a los estudiantes de 5º y 6º semestre, e investigar su contribución a la formación y preparación de los estudiantes para el mercado laboral.

Palabras clave: Recursos Humanos; Proyecto Integrador; Mercado Laboral; Competencias Transversales

1. INTRODUCTION

The appreciation of human capital has become a central theme in discussions of economic and social development over the years, as Sartori and Garcia (2019) note. This concept refers to the set of skills, knowledge, and professional experiences. Historically, the perspective on human capital has evolved, moving from a focus on formal education to a broader approach that emphasizes practical competencies.

Transversal skills, also known as soft skills, are an example of this evolution, given that they are essential in a job market that has become more dynamic and interconnected, where skills such as adaptability and collaboration stand out. For this reason, companies have recognized that, in addition to specific technical skills, the development of these abilities is a differentiating factor when adopted into the organizational culture.

Furthermore, we must consider that most recent graduates do not plan to work for an extended period in the same company; conversely, professional careers are becoming increasingly dynamic with varied experiences. Consequently, it has become essential to seek learning to keep up with technological and current societal changes. As claimed by Minarelli (2020), professionals need to keep their knowledge up to date and develop new skills to remain attractive to other employers or service contractors.

Given that educational institutions are responsible for offering the best teaching practices, we can define the integrative project as a set of interdisciplinary activities carried out throughout the semester, with an emphasis on the student. The project aims to integrate disciplines and problematize relevant themes in the course segment, contextualize the real work environment, and advance towards transdisciplinarity (Santos and Barra, 2012).

Given this scenario, this article aims to understand the role of the integrative projects offered in the human resources management course at Fatec Zona Leste and to investigate their contribution to the development of transversal skills. To achieve this objective, the perceptions of human resources students regarding the course's integrative projects will be analyzed to understand how these experiences influence their training and preparation for the job market.

In accordance with the subject matter, this article seeks to answer the guiding research question: "What is the role of integrative projects in the human resources management course at Fatec Zona Leste?" Via a fundamental qualitative and quantitative analysis, this study is relevant for students to understand the importance of projects in professional training and may offer insights into developing new projects aligned with market needs.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Human Resources and the Enhancement of Human Capital

The Industrial Revolution played a crucial role in the creation of the Human Resources sector, as the transformation of labor relations and the need to

manage a growing, diverse workforce led to the formalization of recruitment, training, and employee development practices. With the need to manage relationships between employees and employers, significant changes in work Dynamics occurred, driving the field's development, which has since expanded, facing many challenges and responsibilities that were not previously considered (Oliveira and Macêdo, 2020).

According to Chiavenato (2009), as human resource management developed, other terms emerged. Previously, the terms used included personnel administration, industrial relations, and human relations. Recently, terms such as people development, organizational behavior, and organizational climate have come into use.

Along with the terminology, the objectives of the area have changed over the years. In the current context, Marras (2011) states that the area aims to collaborate and assist in formulating organizational guidelines, thereby influencing the profile of results and, consequently, the company's profits. The same author also emphasizes that, for this to be effective, it is vital to understand how to value human capital within the enterprise.

Human capital refers to the skills and abilities of professionals who help create high-quality products and services to attract and satisfy customers. It consists of knowledge, experiences, and values, forming intangible assets that are fundamental to organizational success (Marques and Palmeira, 2011).

Chiavenato (2009) emphasizes that human capital is composed of intangible assets, encompassing internal, external, and human capital, which are fundamental to the functioning of a company. Furthermore, the people who make up the organization are considered intellectual resources that need to be valued and preserved. Also, as stated by Chiavenato (2009), human capital is not fleeting; it involves valuable people who must be constantly encouraged to develop, contributing positively to companies and ensuring their continuity.

Hence, for companies, it is essential to focus on attracting, retaining, and developing human capital, as they are the key factors in competitive advantage. Marques and Palmeira (2011) emphasize that human capital is directly linked to employees' qualifications, including their training, satisfaction, turnover, and flexibility. The same authors also highlight the importance of investing in this capital to address competition-related challenges, as it is fundamental to innovation and organizational renewal.

2.2 Cross-cutting Competencies and their relationship with Integrative Projects

The concept of competencies has generated extensive debate in recent years, particularly in education and vocational training. In contemporary society, these two aspects are closely related, as education produces knowledge, while companies act as economic agents that require a workforce qualified by educational institutions (Sartori and Garcia, 2019).

Moreno (2006) defines transversal competencies as a set of skills and knowledge that can be applied in different contexts and areas of activity throughout life,

being essential mainly for the performance of work activities, as they go beyond the specific technical skills of a profession. These competencies include communication, teamwork, problem-solving, planning, and company, among others. The same author also emphasizes that they can be considered key, generic, or transferable competencies that are fundamental for adaptation and success in an increasingly demanding and competitive job market.

The Integrative Project is an interdisciplinary pedagogical approach composed of stages that serve as the central axis of the curriculum, promoting the integration of knowledge and a comprehensive vision in the student's education. Through this approach, the integrative project fosters skill development, encourages teamwork, systematic research, and collaboration among faculty, among other factors required for each project (Santos and Barra, 2012).

Santos and Barra (2012) emphasize that, in practice, the integrative project, in addition to promoting interdisciplinarity, fosters the transversality of competencies, establishes relationships between disciplines, and facilitates the improvement of knowledge throughout the academic semester. The same authors also state that a well-structured curriculum that fosters interdisciplinarity helps students understand the real work environment, as projects are often presented with themes aligned with the course area.

As Sartori and Garcia (2019) claim, the relationship between the university and the job market is evident in students' preparation for the professional market. Following this idea, we consider that the content demanded in the educational environment, when applied in integrative projects that are similar to professional life, supports the development of transversal skills. Furthermore, the same authors state that "this relationship is explained by one of the crucial characteristics of the technological college (FATEC), which is the job market in education and not education for the job market."

Based on the above, the Human Resources Management technology course offered by the Faculty of Technology (FATEC) of the East Zone proposes integrative projects in its curriculum, as shown in Figure 1. In accordance with the information provided in the pedagogical project, the course aims to develop students' technical and interpersonal skills for working in planning, evaluation, people management, and other processes related to business and service operations in private companies and public institutions (Maiellaro, 2023).

Technological education encompasses the training of professionals to prepare students for societal transformations. Sartori and Garcia (2019) highlight the role of FATEC in the development and acquisition of skills, as a "holder" and disseminator of knowledge, and as an essential factor in students' insertion into the job market. The authors also mention that another important characteristic of FATEC is its specific focus, "unlike conventional undergraduate courses, the institution aims to train professionals as stated by the market demand of each region."

Figure 1 – HR curriculum matrix of FATEC Zona Leste

1º semestre	2º semestre	3º semestre	4º semestre	5º semestre	6º semestre
Projeto Integrador I - online (40 aulas)	Projeto Integrador II - online (40 aulas)	Projeto Integrador III - online (40 aulas)	Projeto Integrador IV - online (40 aulas)	Remuneração Estratégica (80 aulas)	Planejamento Estratégico em Recursos Humanos (80 aulas)
Psicologia Organizacional (80 aulas)	Captação e Seleção de Talentos (80 aulas)	Gestão das Rotinas de Pessoal I (80 aulas)	Gestão das Rotinas de Pessoal II (80 aulas)	Gestão de Projetos (80 aulas)	Coaching e Consultoria em Gestão de Recursos Humanos (80 aulas)
Comportamento Organizacional (80 aulas)	Gestão das Relações Interpessoais (40 aulas) Gestão de Carreira (40 aulas)	Legislação Trabalhista e Previdenciária (80 aulas)	Educação Corporativa (80 aulas)	Empreendedorismo e Gestão da Inovação (80 aulas)	Auditoria e Qualidade em Gestão de Pessoas (80 aulas)
Informática Aplicada e Gestão de Pessoas (40 aulas)	Competências Gerenciais (40 aulas)	Gestão da Qualidade de Vida no Trabalho (80 aulas)	Gestão por Competência (80 aulas)	Contabilização e Provisão de Recursos Humanos (80 aulas)	Gestão do Conhecimento (80 aulas)
Teoria da Administração (80 aulas)	Ética e Responsabilidade Social Empresarial (40 aulas)	Gestão de Benefícios (40 aulas)	Gestão Financeira (80 aulas)	Gestão de Desempenho (40 aulas)	Sistemas Gerenciais (80 aulas)
Matemática Elementar (80 aulas)	Estatística (80 aulas)	Cooperação e Gestão de Riscos (40 aulas)	Gestão do Clima Organizacional (40 aulas)	Gestão de Saúde e Segurança Ocupacional (40 aulas)	
Litura e Produção de Textos (40 aulas)	Comunicação Empresarial (80 aulas)	Comunicação Interna (40 aulas)	Métodos para Produção do Conhecimento (40 aulas)	Projetos de Recursos Humanos I - online (40 aulas)	Projetos de Recursos Humanos II - online (40 aulas)
Inglês I - online (40 aulas)	Inglês II - online (40 aulas)	Inglês III - online (40 aulas)	Inglês IV - online (40 aulas)	Espanho I - online (40 aulas)	Espanho II - online (40 aulas)
Atividades Externas à Matriz					
Estágio Curricular Supervisionado (ECS) - 240 horas					
ECS (240 Horas)					
Trabalho de Graduação (TG)					
TG (160 Horas)					
aulas/horas semanais: 24a/20h semestrais: 480a/400h	aulas/horas semanais: 24a/20h semestrais: 480a/400h	aulas/horas semanais: 24a/20h semestrais: 480a/400h	aulas/horas semanais: 24a/20h semestrais: 480a/400h ECS: 80 horas	aulas/horas semanais: 24a/20h semestrais: 480a/400h ECS: 80 horas TG: 80 horas	aulas/horas semanais: 24a/20h semestrais: 480a/400h ECS: 80 horas TG: 80 horas
DISTRIBUIÇÃO DAS AULAS POR EIXO FORMATIVO					
Básicas		Profissionais		Línguas e Multidisciplinares	
Aulas	%	Aulas	%	Aulas	%
Matemática e Estatística	160 5,6	Projetos (Integrador, Acadêmico, ANP, etc)	160 5,6	Comunicação em Língua Portuguesa	120 4,2
Metodologias de Pesquisa	40 1,4	Tecnológicas Específicas para o Curso	1680 58,3	Comunicação em Língua Estrangeira	240 8,3
Administração e Economia	80 2,8	Tecnológicas Gerais	160 5,6	Multidisciplinar / Transversal	80 2,8
		Gestão	160 5,6		
TOTAL	280 9,7	TOTAL	2160 75,0	TOTAL	440 15,3

Source: Adapted from Maiellaro (2023)

3. METHOD

The method used in this article combines qualitative and quantitative approaches to obtain a comprehensive, detailed view of the function of integrative projects. The qualitative approach is based on the bibliographic analysis of books, articles, and academic journals. Severino (2007) states that this approach allows for a deeper understanding of the topic and knowledge about the subject. On the other hand, the quantitative method involves quantifying data collected via a structured questionnaire using a Likert scale, as Richardson (1989) indicates.

For data collection, a questionnaire was created using Google Forms, then sent to the semester representatives, and subsequently forwarded to the students in the convenience sample, composed of students from the 5th and 6th semesters of the Human Resources Management course at Fatec Zona Leste. This sampling choice aims to capture the students' specific perception of the position of integrative projects. The quantitative data are analyzed using descriptive

methods, providing insights into students' opinions on the competencies developed in the projects.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As mentioned earlier, the questions were formulated and administered via Google Forms. We estimate that the 5th and 6th semesters of the HR course currently have 52 enrolled students, and, for the data collection of this research, we had 17 participants, with the highest participation from 6th-semester students, as shown in Graph 1.

Source: Authors (2024)

It is important to note that, as shown in the following graphs, students' perceptions of integrative projects vary with their experience throughout their training. With this in mind, the sample's diversity is relevant, as it offers insight into students' experiences in the projects.

As we can see, Graph 2 addresses students' perception of how much integrative projects contribute to their education. Most students believe that projects contribute to their education by promoting meaningful, experiential learning, which is essential for internalizing the content. This shows that the approach to projects is an integral part of education, aligns

The course's pedagogical proposal and the skills required in the job market indicate that the curriculum structure is attentive to external demands and professional challenges.

Figure 2 – Contribution of projects to training

Source: Authors (2024)

Chart 3 – I believe that the integrative projects helped me develop practical skills similar to professional practice.

Source: Authors (2024)

Chart 4 – The themes of the integrative projects are relevant to the job market.

Source: Authors (2024)

As shown in graph 3, 14 students state that the projects helped develop practical skills similar to those of professional practice; therefore, we can affirm that the projects promote the development of competencies. On the other hand, regarding the relevance of the project themes (graph 4), a considerable portion were neutral or disagreed with this question, falling only behind the perception of the majority who agree or strongly agree with this statement.

Chart 5 – The integrative projects helped me develop transversal skills

Source: Authors (2024)

Figure 6 – The integrative projects facilitated the application of theoretical knowledge acquired during the course

Fonte: Autoras (2024)

The graphs above show students' perceptions of the application of theoretical knowledge acquired throughout the course and the development of transversal skills, also known as soft skills, which, as Moreno (2006) maintains, include communication, teamwork, problem-solving, planning, and corporation, among others. According to graph 5, integrative projects facilitate the application of students' theoretical knowledge and help develop soft skills, as shown in graph 6.

Chart 7 – Integrative projects are an essential part of the course curriculum

Source: Authors (2024)

As shown in graph 7, students' perception of the function of integrative projects is positive, as the majority agree that the projects are an essential part of the

course curriculum.

5. CONCLUSION

This article aimed to analyze the impact of integrative projects on the Human Resources Management course at Fatec Zona Leste, focusing on the perceptions of 5th- and 6th-semester students, who represent 32% of the sample. The research sought to identify how these projects contribute to academic training and the development of practical skills essential to the job market, and to evaluate student engagement and the challenges encountered throughout their execution. The results reveal that the integrative projects align with the course's pedagogical plan, as shown in Graph 2, and are consistent with Sartori and Garcia's (2019) findings: unlike conventional undergraduate courses, FATEC aims to train professionals in line with market demand. Furthermore, students attributed high relevance to the integrative projects, especially for developing transversal skills such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving. This aligns with the idea that projects play a fundamental position in shaping a professional profile prepared and aligned with the demands of the job market.

Integrative projects can be considered an effective pedagogical practice, as they train professionals capable of meeting the specific demands of the Human Resources area. These projects not only reinforce theoretical knowledge but also develop practical skills, aligning with market demands. For future studies, it is recommended to explore the relationship between the skills acquired through this methodology and graduates' performance in the job market, analyzing the direct impact on employability and the ongoing development of trained professionals.

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